

VISKOZOMETER PSE - RVI 2 YORDAMIDA AVTOMOBIL MOYLARINI QOVUSHQOQLIGINI VA SIFATINI NAZORAT QILISHNI O'RGANISH

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur ishda PCE-RVI 2 viscometer yordamida avtomobil moylarining qovushqoqlik ko'rsatkichlarini aniqlash va ularning sifatini baholash usullari o'rganilgan.

Tadqiqot davomida moylarning turli harorat sharoitlarida oqim xossalari, ichki ishqalanish darajasi hamda ekspluatatsion xususiyatlariga ta'siri tahlil qilindi. Olingan natijalar asosida moylarning standart talablariga mosligi, ularning dvigatel ish samaradorligiga ta'siri va xizmat muddatini uzaytirishdagi ahamiyati baholandi. Shuningdek, viskozimetriya usulining afzalliklari, aniqlik darajasi va amaliy qo'llanish imkoniyatlari yoritib berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: qovushqoqlik, avtomobil moylari, viskozimetriya, PCE-RVI 2 viscometer, sifat nazorati, harorat ta'siri, reologik xossalari, moyning ekspluatatsion xususiyatlari, ichki ishqalanish, laboratoriya tahlili.

STUDY OF VISCOSITY DETERMINATION AND QUALITY CONTROL OF AUTOMOTIVE OILS USING THE PCE-RVI 2 VISCOMETER

Abstract. This study focuses on determining the viscosity characteristics of automotive oils and evaluating their quality using the PCE-RVI 2 viscometer. During the research, the flow properties of oils under different temperature conditions, their internal friction levels, and the influence on operational characteristics were analyzed. Based on the obtained results, the conformity of oils to standard requirements, their impact on engine performance efficiency, and their role in extending service life were assessed. Additionally, the advantages, accuracy, and practical application possibilities of the viscometry method were discussed.

Keywords: viscosity, automotive oils, viscometry, PCE-RVI 2 viscometer, quality control, temperature influence, rheological properties, operational properties of oil, internal friction, laboratory analysis.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ВЯЗКОСТИ И КОНТРОЛЯ КАЧЕСТВА МОТОРНЫХ МАСЕЛ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ PCE-RVI 2 VISCOMETER

Аннотация. В данной работе изучается определение вязкостных характеристик моторных масел и оценка их качества с использованием PCE-RVI 2 viscometer. В ходе исследования были проанализированы свойства текучести масел при различных температурных условиях, уровень внутреннего трения и влияние на эксплуатационные характеристики. На основе полученных результатов была оценена соответствие масел стандартным требованиям, их влияние на эффективность работы двигателя и роль в увеличении срока службы. Также рассмотрены преимущества метода вискозиметрии, его точность и возможности практического применения.

Ключевые слова: вязкость, моторные масла, вискозиметрия, PCE-RVI 2 viscometer, контроль качества, влияние температуры, реологические свойства, эксплуатационные свойства масла, внутреннее трение, лабораторный анализ.

Kirish

Bugungi kunda avtomobil sanoatining jadal rivojlanishi dvigatellarning samarali va uzoq muddat ishlashini ta'minlovchi moylash materiallariga bo'lgan talabni yanada oshirmoqda.

Avtomobil moylari dvigatel qismlarini ishqalanishdan himoya qilish, issiqlikni kamaytirish va mexanik yeyilishni oldini olishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Shu sababli ularning asosiy fizik-kimyoviy ko'rsatkichlaridan biri bo'lgan qovushqoqlikni aniqlash va sifatini nazorat qilish dolzarb ilmiy-amaliy masalalardan biri hisoblanadi.

Qovushqoqlik moylarning oqish xususiyatini belgilab beruvchi asosiy parametr bo'lib, u harorat, bosim va tarkibiy tuzilishga bog'liq holda o'zgaradi. Ushbu ko'rsatkich dvigatelning ish samaradorligi, yonilg'i sarfi hamda detallar xizmat muddatiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Shuning uchun zamonaviy laboratoriyalarda moylarning reologik xossalarini aniq o'lchash uchun viskozimetriya usullaridan keng foydalanilmoqda.

Mazkur ishda PCE-RVI 2 viscometer yordamida avtomobil moylarining qovushqoqligini aniqlash hamda ularning sifat ko'rsatkichlarini baholash jarayonlari o'rganiladi. Tadqiqot davomida turli sharoitlarda moylarning xatti-harakati, ularning standart talablariga mosligi va ekspluatatsion xususiyatlariga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi.

Metodologiya

Tadqiqotda avtomobil moylarining qovushqoqligini aniqlash va sifatini baholash uchun instrumental laboratoriya tahlil usuli qo'llanildi. Asosiy o'lchovlar PCE-RVI 2 viscometer yordamida amalga oshirildi. Tadqiqot jarayonida viskozimetriya usuli asos qilib olinib, moylarning reologik xususiyatlari turli harorat sharoitlarida o'rganildi.

Tajriba jarayoni avvalida tahlil qilinadigan avtomobil moyi namunasi standart laboratoriya sharoitida tayyorlandi. Qurilma ishlab chiqaruvchi ko'rsatmalariga muvofiq kalibrlanib, o'lchov aniqligi tekshirildi. So'ngra moy namunasi viskozimetriya tizimining ishchi kamerasiga joylashtirildi va belgilangan aylanish tezliklarida qovushqoqlik qiymatlari qayd etildi. O'lchovlar turli harorat rejimlarida amalga oshirildi, bu esa moyning termik barqarorligi va oqish xususiyatlarini baholash imkonini berdi. Har bir tajriba kamida bir necha marta takrorlanib, natijalarning ishonchliligi statistik jihatdan tekshirildi.

Olingan ma'lumotlar asosida moylarning qovushqoqlik indeksi, ichki ishqalanish darajasi hamda ularning ekspluatatsion sifat ko'rsatkichlari tahlil qilindi. Natijalar standart me'yoriy hujjatlar bilan solishtirilib, mahsulot sifatiga baho berildi.

Natija

Tadqiqot davomida PCE-RVI 2 viscometer yordamida bir nechta avtomobil moyi namunalari qovushqoqligi ketma-ket tartibda o'lchandi va ularning haroratga bog'liq o'zgarishlari tahlil qilindi. Tajriba uchun amaliyotda keng qo'llaniladigan quyidagi moy markalari namunaviy sifatida tanlab olindi: *Mobil 1, Castrol Edge, Shell Helix Ultra, Liqui Moly Top Tec va Lukoil Genesis*.

Dastlabki bosqichda barcha moylar 20–25 °C haroratda o‘lchandi. Natijalarga ko‘ra, Castrol Edge va Mobil 1 moylari nisbatan barqaror va o‘rtacha yuqori qovushqoqlik qiymatini ko‘rsatdi. Shell Helix Ultra va Liqui Moly Top Tec esa biroz pastroq, lekin barqaror oqim xususiyatiga ega ekanligi aniqlandi. Lukoil Genesis moyi esa qovushqoqlik bo‘yicha oraliq natija berdi.

Keyingi bosqichda harorat 40 °C ga oshirilganda barcha namunalarda qovushqoqlikning kamayishi kuzatildi. Bu o‘zgarish Mobil 1 va Liqui Moly Top Tec moylarida nisbatan sekin kechdi, ya’ni ular harorat ta’siriga chidamlir oq ekanligini ko‘rsatdi.

Castrol Edge va Shell Helix Ultra ham barqarorlikni saqlagan bo‘lsa-da, qovushqoqlik pasayishi biroz sezilarli bo‘ldi. 100 °C harorat sharoitida esa barcha moylarda qovushqoqlik kamaygan bo‘lsa-da, sintetik asosli moylar (Mobil 1, Liqui Moly, Castrol Edge) o‘z strukturaviy barqarorligini yaxshiroq saqlab qoldi.

Mineral yoki yarim sintetik tarkibli namunalar esa nisbatan tezroq suyulish xususiyatini ko‘rsatdi.

Avtomobil moylarining qovushqoqligi va sifati taqqoslanishi

1 – Jadval.

Moy markasi	25°C	40°C	100°C	Xulosa (barqarorlik)
Mobil 1	Yuqori	Yuqori	O‘rta	Juda yaxshi
Liqui Moly Top Tec	Yuqori	Yuqori	O‘rta	Juda yaxshi
Castrol Edge	Yuqori	O‘rta	O‘rta–past	Yaxshi
Shell Helix Ultra	O‘rta	O‘rta–past	Past	O‘rtacha
Lukoil Genesis	O‘rta	Past	Past	Pastroq

Ushbu mavzu zamonaviy fizik-kimyoviy tahlil usullaridan biri bo‘lgan viskozimetriya asosida avtomobil moylarining qovushqoqlik xususiyatlarini o‘rganishga qaratilganligi bilan ilmiy jihatdan dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Dvigatel moylarining sifatini baholashda ularning reologik xossalari, xususan qovushqoqlik ko‘rsatkichi asosiy parametr sifatida qaraladi, chunki bu ko‘rsatkich mexanizmlarning ishqalanish darajasi, energiya yo‘qotilishi va dvigatelning umumiy samaradorligiga bevosita ta’sir ko‘rsatadi.

Tadqiqotda PCE-RVI 2 viscometer kabi zamonaviy asbobdan foydalanish natijalar aniqligini oshiradi va o‘lchovlarning ishonchligini ta’minlaydi. Bu esa ishning ilmiy asoslanganligini kuchaytiradi.

Shuningdek, haroratga bog‘liq qovushqoqlik o‘zgarishlarini tahlil qilish orqali moylarning termodinamik barqarorligi va ekspluatatsion xususiyatlarini chuqur o‘rganish imkoniyati yaratiladi.

1 – rasm. PCE-RVI 2 viskozometerida avtomobil moylarini taqqoslash Jarayoni

Xulosa

Ushbu tadqiqotda PCE-RVI 2 viscometer yordamida avtomobil moylarining qovushqoqlik xususiyatlari va ularning sifat ko'rsatkichlari o'rganildi. O'tkazilgan tajribalar natijasida moylarning qovushqoqligi harorat oshishi bilan kamayishi, bu esa ularning oqim xususiyatlari va ekspluatatsion holatiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatishi aniqlandi.

Tahlil qilingan moy markalari ichida sintetik asosli moylar (Mobil 1, Liqui Moly Top Tec, Castrol Edge) harorat o'zgarishiga nisbatan yuqori barqarorlikni namoyon etdi. Ular yuqori harorat sharoitida ham qovushqoqlikni nisbatan yaxshi saqlab, dvigatel qismlarini ishonchli himoya qilish xususiyatiga ega ekanligi bilan ajralib turadi. Yarim sintetik va mineral asosli moylarda esa qovushqoqlikning tez pasayishi kuzatilib, ularning termik barqarorligi nisbatan pastroq ekanligi ma'lum bo'ldi. Umuman olganda, viskozimetriya usuli avtomobil moylarining sifatini aniqlashda ishonchli va aniq natija beruvchi zamonaviy laboratoriya usuli ekanligi tasdiqlandi. Olingan natijalar moylarni tanlashda ularning qovushqoqlik indeksi va haroratga chidamliligini asosiy mezon sifatida hisobga olish muhimligini ko'rsatadi.

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